

- BIR1-ASSOCIATED KINASE 1 (BAK1) is a coreceptor and positive regulator of PTI.
- BAK1-INTERACTING RECEPTORS (BIRs) negatively regulate BAK1 complex formation and cell death.
- BAK1 and BIR3 perturbation is guarded by the TNL CONSTITUTIVE SHADE AVOIDANCE 1 (CSA1)
- BIR proteins link PTI to ETI receptors.
- BAK1 interaction and cell death suppression are antagonistically distributed within the BIR family.
- Our research aims to elucidate the structural and functional diversification of the BIR protein family and how evolutionary dynamics have shaped them.

BAK1/BIR3 suppress CSA1-mediated cell death

CSA1 is required for cell death in *bak1 bir3* double mutants. CSA1-mediated cell death is likely suppressed via direct interaction, as confirmed in Split-Luc assays. For more details on this topic please refer to Schulze et al. 2022.

Schulze, Yu et al. Cell Host & Microbe 2022 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chom.2022.11.001>

BIR functional traits are antagonistically distributed within the BIR family

Are BIR interaction interfaces determinants of BIR3 function?

AlphaFold predicted interface residues are required for BIR3 BAK1 interaction

AlphaFold modelling reveals interaction interfaces between BIR3 and BAK1 kinase domains (KDs). Split luciferase assays using the kinase domains of BIR3 and BAK1 reveal that a single K→E substitution in BIR3's interface markedly weakens their interaction.

AlphaFold predicted interface residues are required for BIR3 CSA1 interaction

Mutating key interface residues (MM-Multiple Mutation of 7 key residues) in the CSA1 TIR domain significantly reduces its interaction with BIR3, as shown through split luciferase assays. However, single point mutations of Arginine and Valine also lead to significant reduction of interaction of CSA1 TIR with BIR3.

Modelling of BIR3 interfaces reveals overlapping interfaces with BAK1 & CSA1

The interfaces of CSA1 and BAK1 with BIR3 comprise identical BIR3 areas, suggesting that a tripartite complex with BIR3, BAK1 and CSA1 may not be feasible.

CSA1 weakens BIR3-BAK1 interaction

NC: PNL - BIR3
PC: BAK1 - BIR3
T1: BAK1 - BIR3 + 0.2OD CSA1
T2: BAK1 - BIR3 + 1 OD CSA1

Split luciferase data suggests competitive binding of BAK1 and CSA1 to BIR3.

BIR3 residues differentially bind BAK1 & CSA1

NC: BAK1 - BIR3
T1: BIR3 - CSA1 TIR
T2: BIR3 H→E - BAK1
T3: BIR3 H→E - CSA1 TIR

BIR3 common interface mutation differentially affects interaction with BAK1 and CSA1.

BIR3 Interface residues are mostly conserved in CSA1 TIR interaction

Consurf analysis reveals that the interface residues of BIR3 interacting with the CSA1 TIR domain are predominantly conserved, highlighting their functional importance.

Summary:

- BIR proteins can interact with RLK pattern recognition receptors and NLR effector receptors.
- CSA1 is necessary for BAK1-mediated cell death, linking it to TIR-NBS-LRR-mediated ETI.
- MAMP-triggered immunity and cell death are antagonistically distributed within the BIR protein family.
- AlphaFold structural analyses reveal overlap of BIR3 residues with BAK1 and CSA1, suggesting a tripartite complex is improbable.
- Split luciferase data suggests that CSA1 disrupts the BIR3-BAK1 interaction, aligning with AlphaFold modeling predictions that a stable tripartite complex is unlikely.
- Mutations in overlapping residues of the BIR3 kinase domain significantly reduce its interaction with BAK1 but have minimal effect on CSA1 interaction.
- Mutations in BIR3 kinase domain reduce interaction with BAK1, while CSA1 TIR domain mutations weaken its binding to BIR3.
- BIR3 interface residues with the CSA1 TIR domain are mostly evolutionarily conserved.

Outlook:

How have new BIR subfamilies emerged, adapted and evolved new functions?
Which structural features are determining novel functions evolving in the BIR protein family?